

Guidance for Endoscopy during COVID-19 Pandemic by Bangladesh Medical University Hepatology Alumni Association and its Validation

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15797238>

Article Received 20-03-2025 / Article Accepted 05-05-2025/ Article Published 11-05-2025

ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Corona virus disease-2019 (COVID-19) was declared a pandemic by World Health Organization in early 2020 and the world went into lock-down soon after, which disrupted all spheres of normal life including healthcare delivery. Likewise endoscopy services in Bangladesh were hugely disturbed, which demanded adaptation of safety measures to restart endoscopy during the pandemic.

Methods: This need prompted the Bangladesh Medical University Hepatology Alumni Association to adopt standard operating procedure (SOP) to ensure safe delivery of such services to patients in need. The association also decided to test this SOP to assess its safety and efficacy.

Results: The SOP was tested in a private sector tertiary care center where more than 5,300 endoscopic procedures were performed between April 2020 to December 2021. Results show that only 5 endoscopy staff and 400 patients developed COVID-19, none severe.

Conclusion: The study shows that the SOP adopted by the association was safe and effective and will be useful as we prepare to face the next pandemic sometime in the future.

Keywords: Endoscopy, COVID-19 Pandemic

INTRODUCTION:

Corona virus disease-2019 (COVID-19) caused by novel severe acute respiratory syndrome

coronavirus-2 (SARS-Cov-2) started from Wuhan in Hubei, China and brought the world to a standstill in 2020 spreading rapidly across the globe. World Health Organization declared

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How to Cite

Prof. Mamun Al Mahtab. (2025). Guidance for Endoscopy during COVID-19 Pandemic by Bangladesh Medical University Hepatology Alumni Association and Its Validation. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research*, 6(03), 25-30. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15797238>

COVID-19 a pandemic in early that year [1, 2]. Bangladesh reported the first case of COVID-19 on March 8, 2020 and the first COVID-19 casualty in Bangladesh was recognised 10 days later on March 18, 2020 [3]. The nation went on lockdown on March 26, 2020, which as anticipated hampered our overburdened healthcare delivery system drastically. Like elsewhere in the world, we also rapidly switched to tele-medicine and tele-medical teaching, which was however not enough to meet the demands and requirements of patients who needed interventions like diagnostic and therapeutic endoscopies, radiologic interventions, surgeries etc. to name a few [4].

Not surprisingly, our centre, which hosts one of the busiest endoscopy units of the country saw drastic fall in numbers by 96.7% from March 2020 to April 2020 [5]. Similar experiences were shared by other busy centres in our region as well [6]. We therefore needed to prepare a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) to get back our numbers in order to ensure delivery of the best possible services to our patients in such difficult times, but at the same time ensuring the safety of our patients as well as our colleagues in the endoscopy rooms. However, this was very difficult to accomplish, given the fact that the main route of transmission of SARS-Cov-2 is through respiratory droplets and close personal contact. The risk of transmission of the virus is higher when people get exposed to high aerosol concentration in a close environment for a long time, like in the endoscopy room [7].

The aim of formulating this SOP therefore was primarily to ensure safety of our patients as well as healthcare personnel. Besides judicious use of endoscopy depending to urgency of indications as well as rational use of personal protective equipment (PPE) and appropriate disinfection of endoscopy accessories and endoscopy room were also important considerations.

METHOD:

Members of the Bangladesh Medical University Hepatology Alumni Association were requested by email to give their suggestions about how to conduct endoscopy during the pandemic, achieving the aims of this SOP. Several members came up with their recommendations, which were then

compiled and webinars were subsequently organized to finalize these recommendations. Finally, the association made 34 recommendations for endoscopic procedures for Hepatologists in Bangladesh during the COVID-19 pandemic. These recommendations were compiled under 5 broad headlines (Table 1). Available scientific literature was consulted before finalizing the recommendations. Besides experience of the members of the association and the challenges faced by them, availability of resources and ground realities were also taken into consideration.

Members of the association were encouraged to adopt the SOP in their endoscopy practice. It was further decided to test the SOP at a private sector tertiary centre in Dhaka by a senior Endoscopist to assess its efficacy and to see if it needed further modifications and/or improvements.

SOP for Endoscopic procedures for Hepatologists during COVID-19 pandemic

Background:

Endoscopy units offer favourable environment for SARS-CoV-2 transmission by (i) contact with infected surface or object, (ii) by droplets and (iii) by aerosols.

Considering current COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh, all patients undergoing endoscopy should be considered potentially infected.

Endoscopists and other healthcare personnel are prone to be exposed to SARS-CoV-2 from patients due to close proximity and frequent retching during endoscopy.

Aims:

- Enhance safety of both patients and healthcare personnel.
- Judicial use of endoscopy according to emergency and urgency of indications.
- Rational use of personal protective equipment (PPE).
- Appropriate disinfection of endoscopy accessories and room.

Pre-procedure recommendations:

- Endoscopy will be performed in patients with emergency and urgent/semi-urgent indications.
- In emergency cases (i.e. upper GIT bleeding, obstructive jaundice and acute cholangitis), endoscopic procedure will be performed irrespective of COVID-19 status of the patient.
- Endoscopy should preferably be done under intravenous sedation or total intravenous anaesthesia by a physician trained in anaesthesia.
- In urgent/semi-urgent cases (i.e. oesophageal band ligation, tissue acquisition for initiation of systemic therapy/surgery, biliary stricture and pancreatobiliary stent replacement for non-urgent indication), patients must have SARS-CoV-2 negative report by PCR, maximum within five days prior to procedure.
- Mouth and nostrils of patients will be covered with surgical mask. Mouth guard will be introduced through an opening in the mask.
- All routine or elective endoscopy procedures (i.e. upper GIT screening and assessment of oesophageal varices) shall be deferred until concerned authority announces declining trend of COVID-19 pandemic.
- Such patients will be monitored for any change in clinical status which may change the need for endoscopy to urgent or emergency.

Recommendation for PPE:

- Use of N95 or equivalent mask.
- Extended or re-use of N95 masks should be as per National Guideline of Bangladesh.
- Wear double pair of gloves, one pair below and the second pair above the gown.
- Use of face shield and goggles.
- Wear water-proof gown with hair protection.
- Use footwear cover.

Intra-procedure recommendations:

- Patients shall wear surgical mask.
- Caregivers and/or attendants shall be prohibited from the endoscopy room.

Figure 1: Endoscopic procedures performed in 2020 following the SOP.

SOP for Endoscopic procedures for Hepatologists during COVID-19 pandemic

- Notice will be displayed outside endoscopy room encouraging caregivers and/or attendants to stay away from the room for the benefit of all.
 - Number of staff in the endoscopy room will be kept at minimum.
 - Same team of endoscopy staff will serve the same endoscopy room for the entire session.
 - Personal belongings (i.e. watch, ring, bracelet, bangles, cell phone, stethoscope, etc.) shall not be taken into endoscopy room as these may become contaminated.
 - Healthcare personnel who are symptomatic, suspected or probable COVID-19 must not be involved.
 - Physical distancing must be maintained in the endoscopy room.
 - Chairs and recovery beds should be spaced out.
 - Donning shall be done in a separate room.
 - For disinfection, endoscope and accessories should be exposed to glutaraldehyde-based solution for minimum 2 minutes after each procedure.
 - Availability of hand sanitizers must be ensured.
 - Endoscopy room should be adequately ventilated to the outside by opening windows and/or using a stand fan to blow air outside.
 - Central air conditioning and air conditioning in recycle mode should be avoided.
- Post-procedure recommendations:**
- Healthcare personnel shall not leave the room until all procedures are completed.
 - Doffing shall be done in endoscopy room.
 - Used PPE should be placed in proper container with cover.
 - Alcohol-based or chlorine-based solutions should be used to disinfect.
 - Fogging of endoscopy room should preferably be done.
- Recommendation for post-COVID-19-exposure of healthcare personnel:**
- If a healthcare personnel is exposed to a person at high-risk of or to a confirmed COVID-19 case, infection control team of the hospital must be informed immediately.
 - Guideline set up by the DGHS, Government of Bangladesh must be followed.

Figure 2: Endoscopic procedures performed in 2021 following the SOP

Table1: Standard operating procedure of Bangladesh Medical University Hepatology Alumni Association for endoscopic procedures for Hepatologists during COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 3: Performing ERCP following the SOP

Figure 4: Mask and mouth guard for performing endoscopy following the SOP

Figure 6: Copyright certificate of the SOP for performing endoscopy

Figure 5: Copyright certificate of mask and mouth guard designed for performing endoscopy following the SOP

RESULT:

Once finalized, the SOP was widely circulated and we received positive feedback from the members of the association who had adopted the SOP in their endoscopy practice. Our own experience in the centre was also satisfactory. Not only were we able to continue with endoscopic interventions throughout the pandemic including when the Delta strain struck, we also saw gradual rise in the number of our endoscopic procedures, which almost returned back to our pre-pandemic numbers (Figure 1& 2). Between April 2020 to December 2021, more than 5,300 endoscopies, colonoscopies and endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatographies (ERCP) were performed in that center. Only 5 colleagues got infected with COVID-19. Of them 1 got infected twice. On 14 day follow up, we had 400 patients who had the infection. However none of our patients or colleagues developed severe COVID-19 requiring hospitalization. They all recovered uneventfully following conservative management at respective homes.

DISCUSSION:

Soon after the pandemic broke out, from our region, the Japan Gastroenterological Endoscopy Society and the Chinese Society of Digestive Endoscopy

published recommendations for performing endoscopy during COVID-19 pandemic, as early as in April 2020 [8,9]. These documents were useful for us while preparing our own recommendations. However, at the same time these were also highly challenging for us, as being a resource constrained country with very odd patient to endoscopist ratio, our preparedness and resource availability were nowhere near to those of these two Asian giants.

For example, the Chinese guideline includes pre-endoscopy computed tomography (CT) in addition to polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for SARS-CoV-2 to rule out COVID-19, which was not feasible in our case. So we opted for SARS-Cov-2 PCR and later to COVID-19 antigen testing for exclusion of the disease. They also recommended endoscopies to be performed in special areas where it was possible to prevent COVID-19. Negative-pressure room, medical dynamic air disinfection equipment for continuous air disinfection were few more things among their recommendations [9]. However, these were far cry in our case.

We set out number of recommendations, as already mentioned. Our pre-procedure recommendations advocated endoscopy to be performed for emergency and urgent/semi-urgent indications only. We recommended endoscopy in emergency situations for all patients irrespective of their COVID-19 status. However, in urgent and semi-urgent cases we recommended a negative SARS-CoV-2 PCR report maximum within five days prior to procedure. We further suggested deferring of routine and elective endoscopy till the pandemic was on declining trend.

Ensuring safety of colleagues at the endoscopy room was of utmost importance. For this purpose, we recommended use of N95 or equivalent mask, double pair of gloves, face shield, goggles, waterproof gown with hair protection and footwear cover as integral parts of PPE (Figure 4). However, re-use of N95 masks was allowed, due to scarcity.

For our patient's safety, we made some intra-procedure recommendations, like use of surgical mask and barring of caregivers and/or attendants from entering endoscopy room. Besides, number of staff in the endoscopy room was to be kept at minimum and same team of endoscopy staff was to

serve the entire session. Personal belongings were to be restricted in the endoscopy room. Physical distancing was to be maintained and a separate room was to be designated for donning. For disinfection, endoscope and accessories were to be exposed to glutaraldehyde-based solution for minimum 2 minutes after each procedure and availability of hand sanitizers was to be ensured. Adequate ventilation of endoscopy room was to be ensured by keeping windows open and/or using stand fan to blow air outside. Central air conditioning and air conditioning in recycle mode was to be avoided.

As retching of patients during endoscopy poses serious risk of droplet spread and subsequent of SARS-Cov-2 infection, we recommended that endoscopy be preferably performed under intravenous sedation or total intravenous anaesthesia by a physician trained in Anaesthesia, as there is extreme shortage of specialist Anaesthetists in the country. Besides, surgical mask was to be put on covering the mouth and nostrils of the patients during endoscopy to prevent spread of aerosol. The mouth guard was to be introduced through an opening in the mask, made with a pair of scissors (Figure 3). We designed this mask and got copyright registration for this from the Copyright Office of the Government of Bangladesh (Figure 5).

Healthcare personnel were to be allowed to leave endoscopy room after completing all procedures after doffing in endoscopy room. Used PPEs were to be placed in proper container with cover. Fogging of endoscopy room was recommended. If any healthcare personnel got exposed to a COVID-19 case, infection control team of the hospital was to be informed immediately and guideline set by the Directorate General of Health Services of the Government of Bangladesh was to be followed.

We followed up our patients at 14 days post-endoscopy over cell phone to confirm if anyone had developed COVID-19 or COVID-19 like symptoms. The endoscopy colleagues were also followed up every 14 days for symptoms. We could reach majority of our over 5,000 patients who underwent endoscopy following these recommendations. To our great satisfaction, only 5 colleagues and approx. 7.5% patients had COVID-

19 or COVID-19 like symptoms. None had severe disease requiring hospitalization and recovered uneventfully following home quarantine. This undoubtedly confirmed the efficacy of the SOP developed by our association. Colleagues from Italy reported that only 4.3% patients and 0.6% healthcare workers developed COVID-19, none having severe disease, after endoscopy performed adhering to safety recommendations [10]. Our study however included almost 6 times more subjects compared to the Italian study.

We subsequently obtained copyright registration for our SOP from the Copyright Office of the Government of Bangladesh (Figure 6).

CONCLUSION:

Our results show that the SOP was very effective to fulfil the aims of the study to deliver effective patient care ensuring their safety as well as that of endoscopists and endoscopy staff. This SOP was not only effective during the pandemic, but also has great implications for future as the world prepares to face pandemic X.

Conflict of Interest:

The author declares no conflict of interest in the generation of this manuscript.

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